

METADESIGN: A DYNAMIC FRAMEWORK FOR SEEDING SOCIALLY RESPONSIVE DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This article proposes how metadesign, a systemic, interdisciplinary and emergent design approach, can provide a dynamic framework for carrying out 'Socially Responsive Design' (SRVD) projects. It explores how metadesign tools and thinking can support the development of fledgling community initiatives working within changing, uncertain contexts. In Oslo, Norway, as in many other cities in Europe, there is a shift in demographics taking place due to an influx of new immigrants and an aging population. These mixed communities bring together a variety of cultural practices, social needs and desires. The article presents the findings from the first phase of an SRVD project carried out in November 2011 with the MA Design students at Oslo National Academy of the Arts (KHiO). The project, entitled 'Metadesigning Spaces of Engagement and Exchange' set about 'bisociating diversities' within the community and co-designing 'seeds' to revitalize a multi-cultural shopping and cultural centre in Veitvet, Oslo.

Keywords: Socially Responsive Design (SRVD), metadesign, bisociating diversities, uncertainty, Veitvet Centre.

INTRODUCTION

We are living in an increasingly out of control world, shaken up by the climatic, economic and social instability which dominates our local and international media. The design philosopher Tony Fry defines our current times as the 'age of unsettlement' (Fry, 2011:

2). This describes the large numbers of the human population who are being uprooted and displaced around the globe. Fry predicts that 'a huge design effort (as the alternative to chaos)' will be required to deal with the anticipated changes to our ways of life (Fry, 2011: 2). The following article seeks to understand how designers can embrace these uncertain times to become creative and adaptive 'agents of change' (Tham and Jones, 2008).

Metadesign, the design of design, provides a comprehensive and dynamic framework for responding to uncertainty. It creates 'beneficial affordances by offering a more holarchic, consensual and transdisciplinary approach – i.e. a superset of design' (John Wood cited in Fuad-Luke, 2009: 151). This paper focuses specifically upon how uncertainty is nurtured within the metadesign process in the forming of a design team, the engagement with a local community, and in the holding-back from delivering immediate design solutions to allow for the emergence of collaborative design seeds.

The paper draws upon the findings of a 'Socially Responsive Design' project carried out in November 2011 with MA Design students at Oslo National Academy of the Arts. The project, entitled 'Metadesigning Spaces of Engagement and Exchange', set out to explore the emotional, cultural, social, economic and ecological diversities existing within a multi-cultural shopping and community centre in Veitvet, Oslo. The design students collaborated with Trude Mette Johansen from Bydel Bjerke (the local

council) and key stakeholders involved in the regeneration of Veitvet.

This metadesign process was designed and facilitated by the authors and set out to:

- Situate and explore design within a broader socio-ecological context.
- Foster collaboration with a multi-disciplined team of stakeholders.
- Utilize and evolve metadesign tools and processes.
- Encourage and reveal creative synergies in the team's collaborative work.
- Co-design seeds (i.e. prototypes/ concepts/ scenarios) for creative temporary pop-up enterprises.

The project adopted a team-based approach to mapping the site and 'bisociating' concepts and scenarios for creative, temporary pop-up enterprises that aimed to foster 'diversities-of-diversities' (Wood, 2007) within this community. Here, 'design as planning' was replaced with 'design as seeding' (Ascott cited in Giaccardi, 2005) and 'design as problem solving' gave way to 'design as possibility seeking' (Mizuuchi, 2006) to envision a more creative and sustainable city.

BROADER CONTEXT

SOCIALLY RESPONSIVE DESIGN

'Socially Responsive Design' is a term coined by Lorraine Gamman and Adam Thorpe who are based at the Design Against Crime (DAC) centre at the University of the Arts in London. It defines "design which takes as its primary drivers *social issues*, its main consideration *social impact*, and its main objective *social change*.' (Gamman and Thorpe, 2007). This design approach has been adopted and developed by Maziar Raein and Halldor Gislason at KHiO, Oslo National Academy of the Arts (Raein, 2009). Since 2005, the Masters Design students annually engage in a four-week SRVD project in their first year of study. Raein asserts that 'In order for design to be socially responsive, it must encompass a definition of design that encapsulates and delivers a range of responses that deliver favourable social change' (Raein, 2009). Each year the primary focus of the SRVD project is to give students the opportunity to

become immersed in a local social context, engage with a range of different stakeholders outside of design, and to critically reflect upon social issues and co-evolve design interventions. This is the third consecutive year that the authors have been invited to develop a metadesign process to kick-start the SRVD project at KHiO.

METADESIGN

Where as, in essence, design is a planned, predictive task, metadesign encompasses a collaborative process, 'a shared design endeavour aimed at sustaining emergence, evolution and adaptation' (Giaccardi, 2005). Here an opportunistic process of 'cultivation' follows a process of 'seeding'. The Greek word 'meta' originally meant 'beside' or 'after'. In its common use, today, it also implies change or transformation (e.g. metamorphosis). It therefore implies transcendence or comprehensiveness. Those who facilitate metadesign teams invite participants to integrate their individual identity through several stages of development to be able to 'think-for', 'think-with' and to 'think-as' the team (Wood, Nieuwenhuijze, Jones, et al 2008). We define this process as moving from 'me' to 'we', through cycles of individual and collective action and reflection. (See Figure.1).

Figure 1. A nested diagram of the metadesign process situating the individual designer within a dynamic set of interrelationships with other stakeholders involved in or influenced by the process. On the left hand side is a continuum charting the journey from 'me' to 'we'. The continuum on the right represents an ongoing process of action and reflection.

In this sense, metadesign can be described as being 'co-creative and co-evolutionary, encouraging an unselfconscious (or spontaneous) culture of design' (Wood cited in Fuad-Luke, 2009: 151). John Chris

Jones describes this beyond goal-orientated design process beautifully as ‘shared imaginative living – end-in-itself’ (Chris Jones, 1970).

METADESIGN TOOLS

The ‘Metadesigning Spaces of Engagement and Exchange’ project adapted collaborative tools and processes that were originally developed as part of the ‘Benchmarking Synergy-levels within Metadesign’, Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) and Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) funded research project, at Goldsmiths, University of London (2006-2009). This academic research project explored the notions of ‘synergy’ and ‘metadesign’. The project team developed over eighty metadesign tools for optimising synergy in creative and interdisciplinary teams. An overview of twenty-one of these tools can be found in Alistair Fuad-Luke’s book ‘Design Activism: Beautiful Strangeness for a Sustainable World’ and on the Metadesigners Open Network website (www.metadesigners.org). The tools evolved out of a series of synergy workshops and draw upon methods and research approaches devised by members of the design team as well as methods from design research, management theory, design thinking, Gestalt psychology and story-telling.

In the SRVD project we applied six different metadesign tools throughout the one-week process. The tools were used to introduce all of the stakeholders to each other (1. Cultural Props); to guide the design students from an individual design perspective to becoming part of a team (2. Collective Story-telling, 3. Values Quest); and engaging with the local context (4. Holistic Mapping, 5. Bisociating Diversities); and to work towards the design of collaborative interventions at Veitvet (6. Future Scenarios).

BISOCIATING DIVERSITIES

One of the key metadesign tools that we used for this project is called the ‘Bisociating Diversities’ tool. This tool was originally developed for a project entitled ‘Metadesign tools: Designing the seeds for more creative and sustainable cities’ carried out at the Welsh School of Architecture (Jones, 2009). Arthur Koestler (1964) coined the term ‘bisociation’ in his book ‘The Act of Creation’ to describe the moment when two seemingly unconnected contexts form a new relationship and develop a shared meaning or purpose. Koestler used bisociation to refer to a creative act that is dynamic and unpredictable, belonging to several ‘planes’ of existence. We have applied the concept of bisociation to develop workshop methods that deal with the ‘awkward, clumsy and ambiguous beginnings of creating a design proposal or idea’ (Jones, 2007: 24). In the ‘Metadesigning spaces of engagement and exchange’ project, the teams collected evidence of social, ecological, cultural, economic and emotional diversities in the Veitvet centre. The students worked in teams to illustrate a set of diversity cards and to bisociate their different examples of diversity to create a ‘diversity-of-diversities’ (Wood, 2007). This activity is explored in more detail in the overview of the process.

PROJECT BACKGROUND

THE PROJECT ORIGINS

The project came about as a result of a serendipitous meeting between the SRVD project organisers and Trude-Mette Johansen, the project manager from the Local Authorities (Bydel Bjerke). In this meeting the SRVD mission appeared to align with Veitvet centre’s need for creative input into their regeneration process. Having already conducted both a public consultation and a feasibility study, an overarching strategy for the area was in place.

The owners of the centre recognised the positive contribution that creative practitioners can have in the transition towards a future vision for the centre. They offered a range of designers, architects and artists free office spaces in the centre for a year in return for three days a month of work towards the centre's development and re-branding. This initiative is called *Kulturhagen* (Culture Garden) and has been led by architect Siri Jager Budvik, who runs the Norwegian architecture company Heimstadlaere. The creative practitioners working at Kulturhagen have already experimented with using a grass roots and participative approach to re-imagining Veitvet. This includes setting up a community driven 'open library' and holding a local photography competition entitled 'My Veitvet'.

During this transitional phase the project manager, Trude Mette Johansen from the local authority, identified a need to make the local residents aware that changes were in motion at Veitvet. Holding a

variety social activities and presenting visualisations of the changes taking place in the market place at the centre have worked towards achieving this. Trude Mette explained to the design students that 'the idea is that when people start taking spaces in use, and feel ownership of the center, we can increase the sense of belonging and test out things that can be used in the physical transformation' (Johansen, 2011). As such, Trude Mette and the centre owners were very keen to gather fresh input from the students (See Figure.2). This context provided a favourable situation for the students to carry out 'possibility seeking' and 'opportunity mapping' temporary interventions using the metadesign & SRVD approach.

THE PROJECT CONTEXT

Veitvet centre located in Groruddalen, a suburb of Oslo. Groruddalen is the fastest changing urban area of the capital and is currently undergoing a massive process of regeneration called 'Groruddal's

Figure 2. An observational walk around Veitvet centre – new insights from the students

satsningen 2007-2016'. Oslo City's overarching aim is to 'improve the living conditions and provide 'a better quality of life overall' (Oslo Kommune, 2011). This is due to changes in the needs of local residents, shifts in demography and heavy traffic.

Figure 3. Map of the stakeholders involved with the project at Veitvet centre.

Veitvet at large is an area that houses c. 6000 inhabitants and has the 6th highest immigration density in Groruddalen. Over a period of 13 years (1997-2010) there was a 35% rise of immigrants moving there. Today there are about c.60 different nationalities living in Veitvet, making it a truly multicultural place. It is also undergoing a generational shift in which the elderly are moving out and families are moving in. This has created some socio-cultural tensions in terms of notions of 'identity', 'community' and 'belonging'. Altogether there are a diverse group of stakeholders invested in the future of Veitvet, of which the students became a part of over the course of the project (See Figure.3).

HISTORY OF VEITVET CENTRE

Veitvet centre was once one of Europe's largest and most innovative shopping centres, built in 1958 by the famous construction engineer and Olav Selvaag (Oslo Kommune, 2011). It became a place for pilgrimage where people came from all over the city to visit and shop. The centre also included a library and church and it is still home to Norway's largest bowling alley in the basement. Yet decades later the glory of the place has lost its shine. Competition and changing needs in the area have created a challenge for the owners who have partnered up with the local authorities. They are

seeking ways to revitalise the centre and reframe its purpose and function as a 'cultural hub' for the local residents, alongside offering commercial and public services. The residents want the center rehabilitated. They believe that it is important for the area's reputation. They want the centre to move away from being a shopping *centre* to a *sentrum* a meeting place for the community

OVERVIEW OF THE PROCESS

SRVD: STAGES OF THE METADESIGN PROCESS

The students were guided through four key metadesign stages over the course of the week. These are loosely defined as contextualising, mapping, possibility seeking and seeding future visions. In the first stage, there was a meet and greet workshop where the students engaged with a range of participants in the Veitvet redevelopment project, including residents. There were a series of informal talks where everyone had the opportunity to learn about each other's role in the project. Trude Mette then took the students on a walk around Veitvet (the local context) to explore the site and meet people living and working in the area. In the second stage, the students worked in their own studios at KHiO reflecting upon their personal and professional values. They worked in four newly assigned teams and worked on developing a set of team values. They also created a collective account of the first day and synergy map of the stakeholders including themselves. In the third stage, the students re-visited Veitvet to gather examples of diversities (See Figure. 4). In the final stage, the groups worked together to bisociate their diversities and use the outcomes that emerge from this process (i.e. concepts and questions) to seed future visions. The students learning took place in an on-going cycle of action and reflection (Schon, 1983; Heron and Reason, 2001). The metadesign tools were organised within each of these stages. The process included a series of lectures by the authors on metadesign, ecology and design, design research, social innovation and diversity. There were also a number of individual and team-based workshops and design activities. The stages are briefly outlined in the following sections.

Figure 4. Five Diversities as devised for the 'Metadesigning Spaces of Engagement and Exchange' project

STAGE 1: CONTEXTUALISING

This initial stage of the process is about becoming familiar with the site (i.e. Veitvet centre) and meeting the different stakeholders involved in the regeneration process taking place at Veitvet, as well as the design team facilitating the project. To begin with, the participants introduced themselves by presenting a 'Cultural Prop'. The cultural prop approach is inspired by the cultural probes method (Gaver et al, 2001) and was first developed in the Stored Wisdom project (Sadowska and Tham 2005). The term Cultural Prop was coined in the 'Benchmarking Synergy Levels within Metadesign' project, 2007-2009'. All of the participants were asked to bring along a tangible example of something that represents 'engagement and exchange' in relation to their work or interests. Within the metadesign process we have found this to be a useful tool to break the ice at the start of the process. It also encourages participants to reflect upon their individual background and to generate a shared understanding of the theme of the project. It is from the discussions that take place in this process that we cast the students in different teams.

In this first stage, the students were also provided with a factual background context for the project. This began with an introduction to the concept of 'socially responsive design'. It also included a series of presentations by the various stakeholders involved with Veitvet Centre (e.g. members of the local authorities, a demographics analyst, the owners of the centre, the architects and designers from Kulturhagen). The presentations covered the history of the place, the demographics, a preliminary feasibility study, the owner's vision, and the various creative activities happening on-site.

Trude Mette led the students on an observational walk around the building complex and its immediate surroundings to explore and survey the site. Upon return from the walk the twelve students were cast into four teams of three. The students then took part in a 'collective storytelling' workshop using another metadesign tool. This workshop helps the newly formed teams to process their immediate impressions of the site and to establish a collective narrative (See Figure. 5). The students are asked to share their accounts of what they experienced and learnt on their

observational walk with the rest of their team. This account making takes place in five levels. These are, the sensual, the factual, the systemic, the futures and the whole story. At this stage, interests and assumptions are slowly revealed, creating opportunities for discussion and clarifications in each team. The team also starts to evolve a shared language.

Figure 5. Collective storytelling map.

STAGE 2: MAPPING

This stage was designed to prepare the students for going out into the field. It focused upon introducing the theoretical frameworks that support the project. The students began by reflecting individually upon their personal and professional values. They then worked towards establishing a set of team values in a 'values quest' workshop. This was followed by a 'holistic mapping' workshop where, confronted with a complex situation, they had to identify and differentiate between stakeholders, issues and priorities (See Figure. 6). Here a range of paradoxical issues started to emerge, highlighting complex networks, impacts and interdependencies. These tools also help the students to map themselves in relation to other stakeholders in the project and aim to provide a systemic overview.

Figure 6. Students mapping stakeholders.

STAGE 3: POSSIBILITY SEEKING

At this stage the students were introduced to the notion of diversity. They were asked to collect, in their teams, five different types of diversity (i.e. cultural, social, ecological, economical, emotional) existing within the Veitvet area. Each group collected five examples of each of the five types of diversity. They were then asked to illustrate a set of twenty-five diversity cards. After rapidly prototyping these cards, they moved onto the 'bisociating diversities' workshop activity (See Figure. 7). This process allowed for random and unlikely pairings between diversities to emerge through new and unexpected combinations that would be hard guess or to identify. The students were asked to play games and experiment with bisociating their cards. Amongst the tensions and gaps in between the diversities new opportunities or meanings emerge. Instinctively, the students first came up with concepts or solutions for issues that they had identified around Veitvet. We asked them to turn each of these solutions into questions. The importance here was to refrain from problem solving and to stay open for potential possibilities by continuing to 'fly in the dark'. The aim was to frame as many questions as possible, (i.e. *possibility-seeking questions*) and wait until the next stage of the process before choosing the most challenging and fun questions to pursue.

STAGE 4: SEEDING FUTURE VISIONS

This was the final stage of the metadesign introduction to the SRVD project. Here, the students were asked to select and then reflect upon some of the possibility-seeking questions they had framed in

Figure 7. Diversity cards.

the bisociation workshop the day before. Their next task was to start to ask 'what if?' The students were given a future scenario of Veitvet in 2020. The aim of this future-focused workshop was to steer students to 'think beyond the possible' (Wood, 2007) and to co-evolve their design seeds. This type of activity is a process of making and thinking at the same time. The outcomes from this session were a series of seeds for what we described as 'temporary social pop-up enterprises'. They also worked on a more defined team identity. Already at this stage many of the teams had come up with metaphors and values that created a thread throughout the rest of the project (See Figure. 8).

Figure 8. Beginning of the futures scenario workshop

KEY FINDINGS & DESIGN OUTCOMES

THE SAILORS:

This team worked on a joint venture framework for the local shops to self-organise activities. They created an informal event to bring together the diverse shop owners, some met for the first time despite being located there for many years. Through their research and by using simple and effective graphic design means, the team discovered that by learning about the shop owners and addressing them with personalised invitations as well as a list of all the shops, contact details and opening times in the centre made them all come to the event. This event created a forum for engagement and exchange and highlighted the need for their collective input for the future success of their shopping centre. The toolkit also contained a set of communication guidelines for how to address the local shopkeepers. This was received as a particularly positive outcome for Trude Mette and her team who are continuing to work with building a unique profile for Veitvet centre.

THE JETSONS:

This team created a chandelier of hands to symbolise a volunteering spirit. The team worked with numerous interventions to engage the people who use the centre in what happens there. To 'give a hand' became a metaphor for this and by collecting hundreds of cut outs of the centre user's 'hands' they represented a joint effort in engagement. Their toolkit also contained the blueprint for the design of a local currency entitled 'the hand' which could be used as vouchers for volunteering and other local efforts taking place within the centre initiated by Trude Mette's team.

Figure 9. Veitvet Harbor message in a bottle toolkit

BOTANICAL VEITVET:

This team developed a grow-kit for the local kindergarden. In their future scenario in stage four of

the metadesign process, this team identified waste recycling, closed loop cycles and growth as their key design interests. Inspired by self-sustaining structures,

IF YOU GIVE VEITVET A HAND...

IF WE ALL GIVE VEITVET HANDS...

Figure 10. Illustrations for the 'chandelier of hands' by the team 'The Jetsons'.

they questioned what the public might want from a 'green system'. They realised that the younger generation, the children of Veitvet were naturally curious about these ideas rather than the more skeptical older inhabitants. The children expressed a wish for a garden and so the team's toolkit consisted of a collection of seeds and guidelines for growing plants. The aim of the garden was to create a ritual for spring in the centre's kindergarden.

CRITICAL REFLECTIONS

CREATING A VALUE CRITERIA

The Jetson's reflected upon how the values that they established in second stage of the metadesign process developed into a set of criteria for the team's design work throughout the project. They explained that when they felt slightly lost or astray they would return to their team values, which were: humour, the

unexpected and engagement. This would help them to get back on track with their teamwork and collective vision.

Figure 11. Workshop facilitated by the team 'Botanical Veitvet'.

FORMING A TEAM IDENTITY

Three of the teams stuck together and one team reorganised itself due to external factors such as travel and illness. This showed that the casting of the teams using the 'Cultural Props' in stage one was successful. In the final stage of the metadesign process the teams were asked to decide upon a name. They chose metaphors that connected up to their future scenarios and reflected the team's identity. These names stuck over the course of the four-week project. Notably, 'The sailors' team successfully managed to make use of the metaphor 'the Harbour' for the Veitvet centre. This resonated in their interventions as well as in their final framework for creating a vision towards joint ventures.

HOW TO INVITE IN PARTICIPATION - THE UNFINISHED ATTRACTS

Both the 'Botanical Veitvet' and 'The Jetsons' reflected upon how the unfinished attracted participation in their experiences. Children were more inclined to join in the model making when they could see their contribution. Also, 'The Jetsons' remarked that when they left a knitting project at the centre, the next day they found that locals had continued knitting in their absence. This connects up to the metadesign notion of keeping the process open to 'invite social creativity' (Fuad-Luke, 2009).

DESIGN AESTHETICS ARE LESS IMPORTANT THAN DESIGN'S SOCIAL ACTIVITY

Whilst the design intervention created by the students were observed as being identifiably 'designed', the team's reflected back about how the rough and ready

approach to prototyping didn't take away from the impact of the interventions in terms of the communities response. This connects up our initial definition of socially responsive design where social impact is emphasised over good-looking design (Raein, 2009).

DESIGN FACILITATING INFORMAL MEETINGS

'The Sailors' team discussed the importance of a personal approach and individual exchange. They highlighted the value of designers staging informal meetings in situ at the centre.

CONCLUSION

The 'Metadesigning Spaces of Engagement and Exchange' project represents an example of how metadesign can provide an open and adaptive framework for seeding a socially responsive design processes. Fuad-Luke reflects upon how 'the design environment for metadesign to take place is under-designed to create spaces for others to add their creativity and design, and to permit the system to be evolved by users.' (Fuad-Luke, 2009:151). Through the metadesign process that we have developed for SRVD at KHiO, we have aimed to equip designers with the tools and processes and the confidence for 'flying in the dark'. This process embraces uncertainty in several different ways. Firstly, by facilitating the changing experience of participating as individual designer, to becoming a team member, to becoming a part of a broader community. Secondly, in catalysing the possibility seeking that takes place through exploring the unexpected relationships revealed when bisociating diversities. Finally, through staging the handing over the 'toolkits' to Trude Mette and the local residents. What the students achieved through their own metadesign process was to open up and map a landscape of opportunities for Veitvet's community to evolve further.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the students from the 1st year Masters in Design at KHiO (2011). We would also like to thank Maziar Raein, Thomas Jenkins, Theodor Barth, and Sanneke Duijf at KHiO, Oslo National Academy of the Arts.

REFERENCES

- Fry, T. (2011). *Design as Politics*. New York: Berg.
- Fuad-Luke, A. (2009). *Design Activism: Beautiful Strangeness for a Sustainable World*. London: Earthscan.
- Gamman, L. and Thorpe, A. (2007). *What is Socially Responsive Design? A Theory and Practice Review*. Paper presented at Wonderground conference, Lisbon.
- Gamman, L. and Thorpe, A. (2009). Less is More: What Design Against Crime can contribute to Sustainability. *Built Environment*. Volume 35, Number 3. ISSN 0263-7960. P403-418
- Gaver, W. (2001). *Cultural Probes: Probing People for Design Inspiration*. Paper presented at SIGCHLDK, Interaction Design, August 14-18, Århus, Denmark.
- Giaccardi, E. (2005). Metadesign as an Emergent Design Culture. *Leonardo* 38(4): 342-349.
- Jones, H. (2007). 'Bisociation within Keyword-Mapping; An Aid to Writing Purposefully in Design', *Journal of Writing in Creative Practice*, Intellect Journals. Volume 1, Issue 1. ISSN 1753-5190. Pages 19-31.
- Jones, J., C., c1970. *Design Methods*. London: Wiley Inter-science, John Wiley and Sons.
- Koestler, A, (c1964). *The Act of Creation*. London: Pan Piper
- Mizuuchi, T. (2006). *Relation in Design: A Relational Approach to a New Understanding of Design*. MA Design Futures dissertation. Goldsmiths, University of London.
- Raein, M., (2009). *Socially Responsive Design and Utopia*. <http://designreflections.wordpress.com/2008/11/03/socially-responsive-design-utopia/>. Last accessed on 3rd February 2012.
- Sadowska, N. and Tham, M. (2005). *Minding the Gap: Using artifacts to navigate private, professional and academic selves in design*. *Beginnings: Experimental Research in Architecture and Design*. K. Grillner, P. Glembrandt and S.-O. Wallenstein. Stockholm, AKAD/AXL Books: 54-61.
- Tham, M. and Jones, H. (2008). '*Metadesign Tools: Designing the seeds for shared processes of change*'. *Changing the Change*. An international conference on the role and potential of design research in the transition towards sustainability. Turin, 9th, 10th and 11th July 2008.
- Tham, M. and Lundebye, A. (2008). Design and Emotion conference
- Wood, J. (2007). *Design for Micro-Utopias: Making the Unthinkable Possible, Design for Social Responsibility*. London: Ashgate.
- Heimstadlære Architecture Company
<http://www.heimstadlaere.no/Bokprosjektet.html>
- Statistics Norway:
http://www.ssb.no/english/subjects/02/befolkning_en/. Last accessed 8th February 2012.
- Groruddalen: <http://www.groruddalen.no/master-elever-bruker-veitvet.5001336.html>. Last accessed 8th February 2012.
- For information about the 'Benchmarking Synergy-levels within Metadesign project and the Metadesigners Open Network, please visit <http://www.metadesigner.org> and <http://www.attainable-utopias.com>. Last visited 8th February 2012